

**A STUDY ON DIVERSIFICATION AMONG STUDENTS IN
DHANALAKSHMI SRINIVASAN ENGINEERING COLLEGE,
PERAMBALUR**

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Abstract:

The purpose of the project report entitles a study on diversification among students in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur. The study is focused on the human resource topic as it's valuable resource which is of emotionally controlled and managed in every institution. This project report on study of student's diversification aims at examining the student's adoption level in college culture and environment. For this study simple random sampling method was used and took 110 samples for the study. The research decision is descriptive in nature and primary data were collected for the responds were recorded. Appropriate tools are used to supplement the analysis and interpretation. Tools like percentage analysis were used.

Key Words: Diversification, Interrelationships, Adoption of Cultures and Environment

Introduction:

Diversity is everything that makes people different from each other. This includes many different factors: race, ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, socio-economic status, ability, age, religious belief, or political conviction. All these factors work together to inform how students (and teachers, and everyone else) encounter the world. For the university, diversity means that the campus is viewed as a welcoming environment for anyone who wants to apply. Having an inclusive mission at an educational institution says something progressive and important about their campus that they value diversity and will allow their students to express themselves as they see fit.

Definition:

The University of Rhode Island defines diversity in the classroom as "understanding each student brings unique experiences, strengths, and ideas to our classroom. Diversity is the exploration and incorporation of these differences to enrich learning in our classroom."

Types of Diversity in the Classroom:

In today's classroom, teachers encounter a diverse student body. Some of this diversity is obvious: More than ever, students come from different racial, ethnic, religious and linguistic backgrounds. However, some diversity is not so visible. Students have different learning styles, different levels of motivation and different opinions about the world around them. The responsive teacher should work to recognize and accommodate these different brands of humanity.

Student Background:

America is a nation of many cultures. Students in your classroom, especially in a diverse urban area, are likely to be from many different racial and ethnic backgrounds. You may also encounter students who wear visible symbols of their faith, including young Muslim women who wear the hijab, the head scarf; or young Jewish men who wear the kippah, or skullcap. Some of your students may speak English as a second language.

Cognitive Aptitude:

You will also discover that your students span the spectrum of cognitive abilities. In today's inclusive classroom, you may have a high achiever seated next to a student with a cognitive disability who has a one-to-one aide to help him understand basic concepts. This presents a challenge even for experienced teachers. Differentiated instruction, which used to be accomplished by grouping students into different classes based on their achievement levels, is often now accomplished by giving individualized work to the highest and lowest achievers in a mixed group. While advocates for the struggling students applaud the inclusive classroom, advocates for gifted students argue that this arrangement hinders the development of the best and brightest by expecting them to learn on their own while the rest of the class participates in teacher-led instruction.

Literature Review:

Antonio et al (2015) indicated that racial diversity has positive effects on “complex thinking.” Similarly, McLeod, Lobel, and Cox (2016) found that racially diverse groups performed better on an idea-generation task than did racially homogeneous groups.

Sommers et al (2018) also found that White students who expected to discuss something with a racially diverse group exhibited better reading comprehension than did Whites assigned to all White groups.

Moreland, Levine, and Wingert (2016) argued that diversity is associated with both positive and negative outcomes. On the one hand, negative impacts of diversity concern group cohesion and conflict (see De Dreu & Weingart, 2003); on the other hand, the positive impact of diversity relates to superior group performance (Sommers, Warp, & Mahoney, 2008).

Doving and Gooderham (2015) say about the diversification is a dynamic capabilities have a distinct impact on the scope of related diversification based on his empirical research.

Chakrabarty et al. (2014) say that the diversification negatively impacts performance in more developed institutional environments while improving performance only in the least developed environments.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study on “Diversification” among students in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Permbalur.
- To analyze the interrelationship among students.
- To analyze the students adoption of college culture and environment.

Scope of the Study:

- The study covers the adoption of multicultural students in the college premises.
- The study is conducted to analyze the adoption level of the students in the college.
- The study is conducted to analyze the satisfaction level of the other states students.
- The basic purpose of the study is to analyze the different race and culture are accepted in the college.
- Providing them a safe and secure environment.

Need and Importance:

- Campus cultural diversity enriches the educational experience
- Diversity on campus improves communication
- Promotes personal growth-and a healthy society
- Diversity contributes to expanding the knowledge base and promotes creative thinking.
- The real world is diverse, and a diverse college experience encourages students to think of their careers based on a global
- Diversity is a win-win situation when it comes to social development.

Research Methodology:

A research method is a systematic plan for conducting research. Sociologists draw on a variety of both qualitative and quantitative research methods, including experiments, survey research, participant observation, and secondary data. Quantitative methods aim to classify features, count them, and create statistical models to test hypotheses and explain observations. Qualitative methods aim for a complete, detailed description of observations, including the context of events and circumstances.

Research Hypothesis:

A research hypothesis is a specific, clear, and testable proposition or predictive statement about the possible outcome of a scientific research study based on a particular property of a population, such as presumed differences between groups on a particular variable or relationships between variables.

Null Hypothesis:

A null hypothesis is a type of hypothesis used in statistics that proposes that there is no difference between certain characteristics of a population (or data-generating process).

Alternative Hypothesis:

An alternative hypothesis states that there is statistical significance between two variables.

Sample Size:

Out of the available customers were selected for the study.

Sample size	-	110
Population size	-	257
Sample area	-	Perambalur
Sample unit	-	samples are Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College Student

Statistical Tools of the Study:

Collected data was analyzed with the help of Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur.

- Percentage Analysis
- Chi-Square
- Correlation
- ANOVA

Analysis and Interpretation:

Respondents Based on Relationship with other State Students

S.No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Highly satisfied	18	16.36
2	Satisfied	64	58.18
3	Neutral	22	20
4	Dissatisfied	2	1.8
5	Highly Dissatisfied	4	3.6
Total		110	100

Inference:

From the above table it is observed that the 16.36% of the respondents are highly satisfied with the other state student’s relationship, 58.18% of students are satisfied, 20% of respondents are neutral, 1.8% of respondents are dissatisfied and 3.6% of respondents are highly dissatisfied with the relationship among other state students.

ANOVA Table:

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F
Rows	311.6	4	77.9	1.541
Columns	536	4	134	2.652
Error	808.4	16	50.525	

Interpretation:

Their no significance among interrelationship and participated equally in classroom discussion and learning.

Suggestions:

In our college we need to improve teaching methods for other state students. They have lot of barrier while communicating with their faculty and students regarding doubt clarification in subject. Their study material is different from our study material so the faculty can give some other study material which can be easy to them. Lot of students could not able express their individual spirituality in our college campus so students can encourage other state students.

Conclusion:

Diversity, whether they are disabled, of a different race, gender, or learning abilities. Not only do students with disabilities create different interactions for students, but a diverse learning group simulates what students will face Diversity helps guide students into the most successful they can be, while preparing them for a world of diversity and multi-culture. Students should be in the same classroom where students with disabilities are located, because it causes a conversation. Students face some type of Outside of college in a non-regulated environment. The teacher must be able to control the environment, while still providing education for all the students.

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